

Voltammetric behaviour of pyrantel pamoate at a composite polymer membrane electrode

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Abstract : Voltammetric behaviour of pyrantel pamoate was studied in Britton-Robinson buffer system at composite polymer membrane working electrode. Cyclic voltammetric method has been developed for the determination of drug in pharmaceutical formulation. A well-defined cathodic peak was observed for the pyrantel pamoate in the entire pH range. The current increases steadily with diffusion scan rate and concentration. The results indicate that the process is irreversible and diffusion controlled. This composite film showed good current response.

Keywords : Pyrantel pamoate, composite polymer electrode, cyclic voltammetry.

Introduction

The pyrantel pamoate is very effective against *A. lumbricoides*, hookworms, *T. orientalis* and *E. vermicularis*. Pyrantel pamoate [1,4,5,6-Tetrahydro-1-methyl-2-[2-(2-thienyl)ethenyl]pyrimidine] could be effectively used to control serum mineral levels in children with intestinal parasitic infection¹.

Structure of pyrantel pamoate

Electroanalytical method such as differential pulse polarographic and cyclic voltammetric have been developed for the determination of antihelminthic drug pyrantel pamoate in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation². Electrochemical methods^{2,3} have been widely applied for the determination of pharmaceuticals. In general these methods offer high sensitivity, low limit of determination, easy operation and simple instrumentation.

In recent years, increased interest in conducting polymers has led to a large number of important applications such as for rechargeable batteries, electrosynthesis, in corrosion to protect films, biosensors, modified electrodes and capacitors⁴⁻⁶ etc. Conducting polymers containing

two components can be prepared as copolymers⁷, bilayers and composites. Some properties of two component conductive polymer systems, such as electrical and physical properties can be improved by copolymerization. The mechanical properties of two component conductive polymeric systems may also be improved by polymerization to two monomers, on platinum foil electrodes^{8,9}. Electrolysis of two monomers generally gives a copolymer, as in the case of aniline and thiophene¹⁰. Pekmez *et al.*¹⁰ reported that the thiophene/aniline ratio in the copolymer could easily be adjusted by controlling the polymerization potential.

In the present study, the electrochemical behaviour of pyrantel pamoate has been studied at composite polymer membrane electrode. The main aim of the combination of polycomponent composites, copolymers and blends is to improve the electrical, physical and chemical properties of the homopolymers. In the present paper composite polymer membrane of polyaniline and pyrrole is used as an electrode material for the investigation of electrochemical behaviour of pyrantel pamoate. This composite polymer membrane electrode was prepared electrochemically.

Experimental

The voltammetry experiments were performed using an EG & G Princeton Applied Research Model 273A

potentiostat controlled by the model 270/250 Research Electrochemistry Software 4.30. A three-electrode system was composed of a composite polymer membrane electrode, saturated calomel as reference electrode and platinum wire as auxiliary electrode.

For the preparation of the composite polymer membrane electrode the electrochemical experiments were carried out in an H-type cell. The working electrode was platinum foil having a surface area of 1 cm². The reference was saturated calomel electrode. Preliminary studies revealed that this platinum foil thickness was suitable to produce a free-standing and durable conducting polymer film. The deposition of pyrrole and aniline in a solution of 0.02 M pyrrole, 0.1 M aniline and 1.0 M camphor sulphonic acid at a potential of -0.6 to 1.8 V was carried out on the Pt electrode using cyclic voltammetric technique. The composite film of polypyrrole and polyaniline coated electrode was washed with water and dried in vacuum at 50 °C.

The platinum foil was washed with dilute HNO₃ and acetone and then coated with polymer to provide a reproducible active surface with improved sensitivity and resolution. Then composite polymer membrane electrode was thoroughly rinsed with methanol and double distilled water and gently dried with a tissue paper. The electrode cleaning procedures require only 2 min. All the experiments were carried out under nitrogen atmosphere and at room temperature. The pH metric measurements were made on a digital pH meter (Decible, Db-1011) fitted with a glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference, which was previously standardized with buffers of known pH in acidic and alkaline medium.

Pyrantel pamoate (Nemocid, 250 mg tablet) was obtained from IPCA Pharmaceutical Company, India. KCl (1 mol L⁻¹) solution was prepared in distilled water and used as supporting electrolyte. A stock solution of pyrantel pamoate (1 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹) was prepared in dimethyl formamide (DMF). A suitable amount of pyrantel pamoate stock solution was taken in volumetric flask and DMF was added to make up the volume. The solutions for recording voltammograms were prepared by mixing appropriate volume of sample and the buffer of varying pH. Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5–12.0 was prepared in distilled water by adding suitable amounts of

0.4 M NaOH solution (basic solution) to a stock solution composed of a mixture of 2.14 mL phosphoric acid, 2.472 g boric acid and 2.3 mL of glacial acetic acid (acidic solution). Solution was stirred after mixing and left overnight to attain equilibrium. All reagents used were AnalaR grade.

Procedure : The amount of pyrantel pamoate present in each tablet was 250 mg. Excipients such as microcrystalline cellulose, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose, lactose and titanium dioxide are added to dosage forms. Ten tablets were weighed accurately and crushed to a fine powder. The accurately weighted quantities of these powders equivalent to 2.5 g of pyrantel pamoate were transferred to 50 mL volumetric flask and dissolved in dimethyl formamide. After sonicating and shaking the mixture for 30 min, volume was made up with the same solvent and centrifuged. An aliquot of the supernatant liquid was transferred into a calibrated flask and a series of dilutions were prepared with BR buffers at pH 2–12 and mixed 1 mL KCl as supporting electrolyte.

Results and discussion

The voltammetric behaviour of pyrantel pamoate was examined in the pH range 2.0–12.0 by cyclic voltammetry. Pyrantel pamoate gave one well-defined cathodic peak in the entire buffer system at composite polymer membrane electrode.

Cyclic voltammograms of pyrantel pamoate were also recorded in dimethylformamide at composite polymer electrode at varying scan rates (20–200 mV/s). Cyclic voltammograms show a single reduction peak at -784 mV at 20 mV/s. As the scan rate increased, the cathodic peak potential shifted towards negative potential -930 mV at 200 mV/s (Fig. 1). Plot of $i_{p,c}$ vs $\nu^{1/2}$ (ν = scan rate) is a straight line passing through the origin indicating diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process.

Cyclic voltammograms of pyrantel pamoate at different concentrations at composite polymer membrane electrode are shown in Fig. 2. With the increase in concentration of the drug, a linear relation between peak current and concentration was observed in the range from 1 × 10⁻³ to 4 × 10⁻³ at composite polymer membrane electrode. The peak potential ($E_{p,c}$) shifted towards more negative potential (from -784 to -859.9 mV) on increasing the concentration of the pyrantel pamoate, indicating the

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of pyrantel pamoate (pH 7.9) in Britton-Robinson buffer at different scan rates at composite polymer membrane electrode : (a) 20, (b) 50, (c) 100, (d) 150, (e) 200 mV/s, concn. $1 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of pyrantel pamoate (pH 7.9) in Britton-Robinson buffer at different concentrations at composite polymer membrane electrode : (a) 1×10^{-3} , (b) 2×10^{-3} , (c) 3×10^{-3} , (d) $4 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\nu = 50$ mV/s.

Fig. 3. Plot of peak potential ($E_{p,v}$) vs pH for pyrantel pamoate (concn. $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $\nu = 50$ mV/s) at composite polymer membrane electrode.

irreversibility of the electrode process. Plot of $i_{p,c}$ vs concentration is a straight line at composite polymer membrane electrode.

Cyclic voltammograms using composite polymer membrane electrode were also recorded at different pH. The pH of the solution was varied from 2.0 to 12.0. No anodic peak in the entire pH range was observed. The peak potential values of pyrantel pamoate are dependent on pH and peak current increases with increase in the pH of the buffer system. The influence of several electrolytes (phosphate and Britton-Robinson) on the analytical signal was also studied. With the rise in pH, peak potential is shifted towards more negative values (Fig. 3) up to pH 7.9 indicating the participation of proton in the electrode process.

On the basis CV, chromatographic and spectral studies following mechanism² may be postulated for the reduction of pyrantel pamoate at composite polymer membrane electrode.

Conclusion :

Electrochemically deposited composite polymer membrane electrode on the platinum foil indicates good cata-

lytic current response for the voltammetric determination of pyrantel pamoate drug. The current-voltage characteristic of the composite film was found to be linear which indicates a semiconducting behaviour. This composite polymer electrode also shows good stability with the solvent.

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